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Xist is an authentic p53-regulated transcript.

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We discovered control of Xist by p53 through study of p53+ and p53- breast cancer cells, demonstrating a function for Xist in transformation. We demonstrate here through study of total transcription in the mouse embryo during mammalian development in utero at E10.5 in p53-sufficient and p53-deficient mice that Xist is a *bona fide* p53-regulated transcript.